

Mixed Ligand Metal Chelates of *m*-Cresotic Acid

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Complex forming equilibria in the ternary systems of the type M-DPY-L[M=copper(II), zinc(II), and cadmium(II), DPY=2,2' dipyridyl and L=*m*-cresotic acid (*m*-CA)] have been examined pH-metrically in 50% aqueous-ethanol (v/v) medium. The values of $\log K_{M.DPY.L}^{M.DPY.L}$ (K =conditional formation constant of mixed ligand chelates; 25°, $\mu=0.1M$, NaClO₄) are 9.16, 7.46 and 6.75 respectively for copper(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes. The binary M-L systems were also investigated under identical conditions as those of the ternary systems in order to have a comparative complexation behaviour in both such types of systems. In addition, the experiments in the binary systems were repeated at two other ionic strengths, to obtain the thermodynamic parameters. The values of step thermodynamic formation constants are: $\log K_1^{\mu \rightarrow 0} = 12.00, 9.60, 8.00$ and 7.20 respectively for H⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺, while $\log K_2^{\mu \rightarrow 0} = 4.50$ and 7.45 respectively for H⁺ and Cu²⁺ complexes.

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC investigation of iron(III) complexes of *m*-cresotic acid (*m*-CA) has been carried out by Katiyar and Chauhan¹, while the magnetic properties of its copper(II) complex have been examined by Kratsmar-Smogrovic et al.². Vartak and Menon³ determined the conditional step formation constants of its copper(II), beryllium(II), and uranyl(II) complexes in 50% aqueous-dioxan medium potentiometrically. No work on the mixed ligand complex formation of *m* CA, however, appears to be on record.

Results of studies on ternary complexing systems with copper(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) ions involving 2,2' dipyridyl as a primary and *m*-CA as a secondary ligand are being reported here. The method adopted has been the Irving and Rossotti pH-titration technique⁴ as modified by Chidambaram and Bhattacharya⁵. All the experiments were carried out at 25° and at $\mu=0.1M$ (NaClO₄) in 50% aqueous-ethanol (v/v) medium.

For comparison purposes, the binary metal-*m*-CA complexes under identical conditions as those of the mixed ligand complexing systems were also investigated employing Irving and Rossotti pH-titration technique⁴. The experiments in these binary systems were further repeated at two other ionic strengths (viz. 0.05*M* and 0.2*M*) as well, so as to evaluate the thermodynamic parameters.

Experimental

Solutions and related materials

All the solutions were prepared in doubly distilled CO₂-free water and the reagents used were of analytical grade.

Solutions of copper(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) perchlorates were prepared and standardized⁶. Suitable volumes of these solutions were separately diluted and perchloric acid added if necessary to obtain (i) 0.002*M* metal perchlorate in 0.01*M* perchloric acid and (ii) 0.01*M* metal perchlorate in 0.02*M* perchloric acid. Perchloric acid (0.02*M*) and sodium hydroxide (0.1*M*) solutions were prepared and used after standardization. A stock solution of sodium perchlorate (1*M*) was prepared and standardized⁷. Stock solutions (0.01*M*) of the chelating ligands viz. *m*-cresotic acid (in ethanol) and 2, 2' dipyridyl (in water) were prepared separately by direct weighing.

Procedure :

Measurements were carried out at 25° using Leeds and Northrup pH-meter with a glass-calomel electrode assembly.

M-*m*-CA Systems :

Three titration mixtures viz. (A) perchloric acid + sodium perchlorate, (B) mixture A + *m*-CA, and (C) mixture B + metal solution were prepared at three different ionic strengths, viz. 0.05*M*, 0.1*M* and 0.2*M* maintained by sodium perchlorate. In mixture C no perchloric acid was required to be added as metal ion taken contained acid exactly equivalent to that taken in mixture A or B. Volume of each mixture was raised to 50 ml by adding water and ethanol to obtain a 50% aqueous-ethanol medium. The mixtures were individually titrated against standard alkali and thus three titration curves viz. A, B and C were obtained. For illustration titration curves only at $\mu=0.1M$ (fig. 1) is being given here; similar curves were obtained at other μ values.

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The concentrations were of the order: $N^{\circ}=0.1M$, $E^{\circ}=0.002M$, $TC_{Lo}=0.002M$ and $TC_{Mo}=0.0004M$ in all the systems investigated, and the symbols have their usual meanings⁴.

Fig. 1. Titration curves of $M(II)-m-CA$ system ($\mu=0.1, 25^{\circ}$)

—○—○— acid (A); —●—●— *m*-CA (B); and
 —○—○— copper (Cu), —□—□— zinc (Zn), and
 —△—△— cadmium (Cd) (C)

M-DPY-m-CA Systems: Mixtures containing: (D) perchloric acid+sodium perchlorate+primary ligand (DPY), (E) mixture D+metal solution, (F) perchloric acid+sodium perchlorate+secondary ligand (*m*-CA), and (G) mixture F+DPY+metal solution were prepared. In the mixtures E and G no perchloric acid was required to be added as the metal solution taken already contained acid exactly equivalent to that taken in mixture D or F. Total volume in each case was then raised to get a 50% aqueous-ethanol medium in 50 ml. Ionic strength in each case was 0.1M ($NaClO_4$). The concentrations were: $TC_{Lo}=0.001M$, $TC_{DPY^{\circ}}=0.001M$, $TC_{M.DPY^{\circ}}=TC_{M^{\circ}}=0.001M$ where $TC_{DPY^{\circ}}$ and $TC_{M.DPY^{\circ}}$ are total initial concentrations of dipyriddy and *M*-dipyriddy complex respectively. N° and E° were same as in the binary systems. These mixtures were titrated separately against standard alkali (0.1M) and thus four titration curves, D, E, F and G were obtained which are shown in fig. 2 in *Cu-DPY-m-CA* system. Titration curves of the remaining systems being of similar nature have been excluded to economize the space.

Fig. 2. Titration curves of $Cu(II)-DPY-m-CA$ system ($\mu=0.1, 25^{\circ}$)

—●—●— DPY(D); —○—○— copper-DPY (E);
 —□—□— *m*-CA(F); —△—△— copper-DPY-*m*-CA

Calculations :

M-m-CA Systems: From the titration curves A, B, and C (Fig. 1), the average number of protons bound per free ligand ion ($\bar{n}_A$) average number of ligands attached per metal ion, ($\bar{n}$) and free ligand exponent (p_L) were calculated.

M-DPY-m-CA Systems: Complete formation of 1 : 1 ($M.DPY$)²⁺ complex occurs at $pH \lesssim 4$, which remains stable upto $pH \approx 6$, after which formation of hydroxo complex $M.DPY(OH)_n$ commences. Beyond $pH \approx 9$ the complexes seem to form perhaps the metal hydroxides, which ultimately precipitate out (Figs. 1 and 2). Mixed ligand titration curve G departs from the secondary ligand curve F along the volume axis at a pH above the complete formation of 1 : 1 ($M.DPY$)²⁺ species and below the commencement of the hydroxo complex formation. Further in the titration mixture E precipitation occurs at $pH \approx 9$ while no precipitation is observed in the mixture G at this pH. These indicate that mixed ligand complexation has occurred. Thus average number of *m*-CA molecules attached per ($M.DPY$)²⁺ ion, $\bar{n}_{m \pm \alpha}$ were calculated using equation

$$\bar{n}_{m \pm \alpha} = \frac{(V^V - V^{IV})(N^{\circ} + E^{\circ})}{(V^{\circ} + V^V) \bar{n}_A TC_{M.DPY^{\circ}}} \quad \dots (1)$$

where v' , v^{IV} and v^V are the volumes of alkali to reach

the same pH values in curves A (Fig. 1), and F and G (Fig. 2) respectively. $TC_{M.DPY}^0$ is the total initial concentration of $(M.DPY)^{2+}$ ion, which is equal to the initial concentration of metal ion taken in mixture G. Values of $\bar{n}_A$ at different pH were available from the binary complexing systems. From the values of $\bar{n}_{miz}$ so obtained free ligand exponent pL_{miz} were calculated using the following equation

$$pL_{miz} = \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{n=j} \beta_n^H \left(\frac{1}{\text{antilog } B} \right)^n}{(TC_{Lo} - \bar{n}_{miz} TC_{M.DPY}^0) \cdot \frac{V^0 + vV}{V^0}} \right] \quad (2)$$

Results and Discussion :

The protonation constants of the ligand were evaluated by various computational methods⁴ and the mean values are recorded in Table 1. The thermodynamic values of the protonation constants (obtained by plotting $\log K^H$ vs. $\sqrt{\mu}$, and extrapolating to zero ionic strength) along with the corresponding ligational standard free energy changes (ΔF° , $\Delta F^\circ = -RT \ln K$) are recorded in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

TABLE 1. STABILITY CONSTANTS OF M-m-CA CHELATES IN 50% (v/v) AQUEOUS ETHANOL MEDIUM (25°)

Cation	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2^a$	$\log \beta_n$
	(a) $\mu=0.05$		
H ⁺	11.68	4.18	15.86
Cu(II)	8.97	7.10	16.07
Zn(II)	7.46	...	...
Cd(II)	6.56	...	...
	(b) $\mu=0.1$		
H ⁺	11.56	4.06	15.62
Cu(II)	8.91	6.89	15.80
Zn(II)	7.32	...	...
Cd(II)	6.40	...	...
	(c) $\mu=0.2$		
H ⁺	11.47	4.01	15.48
Cu(II)	8.41	6.82	15.23
Zn(II)	6.99	...	...
Cd(II)	6.12	...	...
	(d) $\mu \rightarrow 0$		
H ⁺	12.00	4.50	16.50
Cu(II)	9.60	7.45	17.05
Zn(II)	8.00	...	...
Cd(II)	7.20	...	...

TABLE 2. LIGATIONAL STANDARD FREE ENERGY CHANGES (ΔF°) IN VARIOUS M-m-CA SYSTEMS IN 50% AQUEOUS-ETHANOL MEDIUM (v/v) (25°, $\mu \rightarrow 0$)

Cation	$-\Delta F_1^\circ$	$-\Delta F_2^\circ$	$-\Delta F^\circ$
H ⁺	16.47	6.17	22.64
Cu(II)	13.17	10.23	23.40
Zn(II)	10.98	...	...
Cd(II)	9.88	...	...

In M-m-CA systems, the $\bar{n}$ values in case of Cu²⁺ ions extend over $\approx 0-1.8$ whereas, with Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ ions, these do not even exceed unity, showing that while Cu²⁺ forms both 1 : 1 as well as 1 : 2 complex species, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ form only 1 : 1 (occurrence of precipitation/turbidity/opacity etc. in case of Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ did not permit the evaluation of $\log K_2$ values). Mean values of the formation constants obtained by various computational methods at different ionic strengths and also at $\mu \rightarrow 0$ are recorded in table 1, along with the corresponding standard ligational free energy changes (Table 2). The order of stability is : Cu > Zn > Cd.

TABLE 3. FORMATION CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND CHELATES AND COMPARISON WITH M-m-CA CHELATES IN 50% AQUEOUS-ETHANOL (v/v) MEDIUM (25°, $\mu = 0.1M$)

Metal	$\log K_{M.DPY.M.DPY.L}^M$	$\log K_1^*$	$\log K_2^*$
Cu(II)	9.16	8.91	6.89
Zn(II)	7.46	7.32	...
Cd(II)	6.75	6.40	...

* Values taken from table 1.

The conditional formation constants in the mixed ligand complexing systems, $\log K_{M.DPY.M.DPY.L}^M$ (25°, $\mu = 0.1$) determined by average value method are recorded in Table 3. From statistical considerations value of $\log K_{M.DPY.M.DPY.L}^M$ should be appreciably less than $\log K_1$, as the concentration of electrons around $(M.DPY)^{2+}$ would be more than $(M.aq)^{2+}$ (dipyridyl being more strongly coordinating than water). However, it is interesting to note that $\log K_1 \approx \log K_{M.DPY.M.DPY.L}^M$ (Table 3). The reason being that the two nitrogen atoms of the dipyridyl molecule form σ -bonds with the metal ion, and in addition to this there exists a strong tendency of M $\rightarrow$ N π -interaction due to the back donation of electrons from metal d π -orbital to the vacant delocalized π -orbital over the dipyridyl molecule^{12,13}. As a result of this back donation, the concentration of electrons around the metal ion in $(M.DPY)^{2+}$ does not increase significantly due to which the electronegativity of the metal ion in this species remains almost the same as in $(M.aq)^{2+}$, which in consequence justifies $\log K_1 \approx \log K_{M.DPY.M.DPY.L}^M$. It may be recalled that Martell and coworkers¹² and Sigel^{11,14-17} have observed in several ternary complexing systems that the value of $\log K_{M.M.L}^{M.L}$ is slightly greater than $\log K_M^M$ when coordination is through two oxygen atoms from the secondary ligand. Our results reported here are in conformity to their findings. The larger value of $\log K_{M.DPY.M.DPY.L}^M$ than of $\log K_2$ (Table 3) may be expected on the basis that in the formation of ML_2 species there occurs coulombic repulsion between the negative oxygens of the two ligand anions tending to lower the stability of ML_2 species, whereas no such repulsion is encountered in the mixed ligand complex formation¹².

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